

Supplementary material for:
Progress variable optimization: Effects on the manifold topology
and reduced-order modeling

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Code and data availability:

All code used to produce the results in the original publication and in this supplementary material can be found in the form of Python scripts and Jupyter notebooks in the public GitHub repository:

`</> github.com/GregoireCorluy/PV-optimization-for-ROM`

All data and code, to reproduce the results, are archived and publicly available on Zenodo:

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Introduction

The supplementary material provides additional information about the results presented in the main paper. It follows the same structure as the main paper with Section S1 providing more details about the effect of the encoder-decoder modifications and the observation on the manifold topology when sparsifying the PV definition corresponding to Section 4 of the main paper, Section S2 discussing the *a priori* comparison between the heuristic and optimized PVs reported in Section 5 of the main paper and Section S3 providing the complete *a posteriori* results presented in Section 6 of the main paper.

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S1 Effects of the encoder-decoder modifications and observations on the manifold topology

This section provides extra information about the improvements and findings of the encoder-decoder discussed in Section 4 of the main paper.

S1.1 The trainable scaling layer

S1.1.1 Hyperparameters being varied for the trainable scaling layer analysis

To compare encoder-decoders with *vs.* without the trainable scaling layer as described in Section 4.1 of the main paper, multiple encoder-decoders were trained with 5 different random seeds and 6 hyperparameter settings. The hyperparameters being varied are the selection of decoded species being transformed to the logarithmic scale and its offset ϵ , explained in Section S1.2. An overview of the hyperparameters being varied is shown in Table S1. Hyperparameter sets 1 and 2 transform only H_2O_2 to the log-scale, sets 3 and 4 (selected for the rest of the paper) transform all the QoIs to the log-scale, and sets 5 and 6 transform all minor species in the log-scale while keeping the main products and reactants in the linear scale.

Hyperset	$Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2}$	$Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	Y_{H_2}	Y_{HO_2}	$Y_{\text{N}_2\text{O}}$	Y_{NO_2}	Y_{NO}	Y_{O_2}	Y_{OH}
1	$\log(\epsilon_{10})$	linear	linear	linear	linear	linear	linear	linear	linear
2	$\log(\epsilon_{20})$	linear	linear	linear	linear	linear	linear	linear	linear
3	$\log(\epsilon_{10})$	$\log(\epsilon_{10})$	$\log(\epsilon_{10})$	$\log(\epsilon_{10})$	$\log(\epsilon_{10})$	$\log(\epsilon_{10})$	$\log(\epsilon_{10})$	$\log(\epsilon_{10})$	$\log(\epsilon_{10})$
4	$\log(\epsilon_{20})$	$\log(\epsilon_{20})$	$\log(\epsilon_{20})$	$\log(\epsilon_{20})$	$\log(\epsilon_{20})$	$\log(\epsilon_{20})$	$\log(\epsilon_{20})$	$\log(\epsilon_{20})$	$\log(\epsilon_{20})$
5	$\log(\epsilon_{10})$	linear	linear	$\log(\epsilon_{10})$	$\log(\epsilon_{10})$	$\log(\epsilon_{10})$	$\log(\epsilon_{10})$	linear	$\log(\epsilon_{10})$
6	$\log(\epsilon_{20})$	linear	linear	$\log(\epsilon_{20})$	$\log(\epsilon_{20})$	$\log(\epsilon_{20})$	$\log(\epsilon_{20})$	linear	$\log(\epsilon_{20})$

Table S1: Hyperparameters being varied to compare f -PV manifolds obtained with *vs.* without the trainable scaling layer. The hyperparameters are the same as described in Section 3.2 except for the QoI set. Next to temperature and the PV source term, the species in the QoI set are in the original linear scale or transformed in the logarithmic scale ($\log(\epsilon_{10}) = \log(Y_i + 10^{-10})$ and $\log(\epsilon_{20}) = \log(Y_i + 10^{-20})$).

S1.1.2 Complete figure of MSE *vs.* cost for the trainable scaling layer analysis

In Section 4.1, Fig. 2 showed how the cost and MSE were related to each other for parameterizations with *vs.* without scaling layer. However, three outliers, *i.e.*, two from encoders-decoders with scaling layer and one from an encoder-decoder without scaling layer indicated in Fig. S1 with red circles, were removed from Fig. 2 as the parameterizations were coming from the training of encoders-decoders that converged to poor parameterizations due to unfavorable random weight initializations. Hence, they exhibited a significantly higher cost and MSE compared to their respective parameterization cluster.

S1.1.3 Complete figure of the weight analysis

To understand the effect of the trainable scaling layer on the manifold parameterization, we performed in Section 4.1 a weight analysis comparing the total encoder weights between encoder-decoders with *vs.* without scaling layer and comparing the scaling and encoder weights of encoder-decoders with scaling layer. In the main paper, Fig. 4 zoomed in on the region where most points laid while here Fig. S2 shows the same figure containing all the datapoints. Fig. S2a depicts the few cases where the total encoder weight is very small in contradiction with the encoder weight of the encoder-decoder without scaling layer staying around 10^{-1} . For Fig. S2b, the scaling and encoder weight of encoder-decoders with the scaling layer stay in the same order of magnitude even when the weights become very small.

Fig. S1: Comparison of the f -PV parameterization obtained with encoders-decoders with *vs.* without the scaling layer. (a) Average QoI cost, \mathcal{L}_{avg} , *vs.* the average MSE of all QoIs with and without the scaling layer. (b) The PV source term cost, $\mathcal{L}_{\dot{\omega}_{\text{PV}}}$, *vs.* the average cost, \mathcal{L}_{avg} , with and without the scaling layer.

Fig. S2: (a) Absolute encoder weights w_i for encoder-decoders without scaling layer *vs.* the absolute total weights $s_i w_i$ for encoder-decoders with scaling layer for every species i and random seed. (b) Absolute scaling weights s_i *vs.* the absolute encoder weights w_i of encoder-decoders with scaling layer for every species i and random seed.

S1.2 QoIs transformed to the logarithmic scale

In Section 4.2 of the main paper, we showed that transforming the QoIs at the decoder's output to the log-scale was beneficial for the optimized parameterization. In particular, with the change in scale, the manifold was stretched out near initial conditions (IC) and steady-state. Hence, we illustrate here for the case of H₂O₂ how the logarithmic scale can affect the manifold parameterization. Fig. S3 compares H₂O₂ with different scales, *i.e.*, the linear scale and the logarithmic scale with an offset ϵ of 10^{-10} and 10^{-20} ($\log(Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2} + \epsilon)$ [1]), with the time in the linear and logarithmic scale. The offset included in the logarithmic scale determines which range of values gets compressed, hence it suppresses the importance of the smallest values near zero and avoids the problem of taking the logarithm of zero. For example, when applying an offset ϵ of 10^{-10} to $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2}$ ($\log(Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2} + 10^{-10})$), all the $Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2}$ below 10^{-10} are compressed around -10 and are therefore down-weighted or even suppressed during training. Visually, the offset influences the slope of the transformed trajectory from IC till ignition, shown in Fig. S3.

To understand how the different transformations of H₂O₂ influences the encoder-decoder, every trajectory is rescaled in the same range and shown in the bottom row of Figure S3. This is explained by the fact that

absolute QoI values do not influence the training of the encoder-decoder as the QoIs at the decoder are rescaled between -1 and 1 during training. On the contrary, the gradients of the QoI over the trajectory drive the training of the encoder-decoder, because these need to be modeled. In case datapoints with varying QoI values are stacked at the same location of the manifold, the decoder would fail to regress the different QoI values. Hence, gradients force the encoder-decoder to stretch out regions where the QoI varies. By comparing all the transformations and rescaling every curve in the range from 0 to 1, the bottom row of Fig. S3 shows that the slope increases from IC till ignition and starts earlier when using the logarithmic scale instead of the linear scale and is even enhanced when using a smaller offset for the logarithmic transformation. This difference in gradient explains therefore why the encoder-decoder will stretch out the manifold near IC when using the logarithmic scale with an offset of 10^{-20} . From the hyperparameter tuning, we found out that applying a logarithmic transformation with an offset of 10^{-20} to all species mass fractions at the decoder provided the most consistently a good manifold parameterization.

Fig. S3: Evolution of H_2O_2 in the linear scale (first row), logarithmic scale $\log(Y_{H_2O_2} + 10^{-10})$ (second row) and $\log(Y_{H_2O_2} + 10^{-20})$ (third row) and all scales together rescaled from 0 to 1 (last row) over time in the linear (left column) and logarithmic (right column) scale for one trajectory of the manifold.

S1.3 Explanation of the decreasing average cost when removing the second most important species

In Section 4.3 of the main paper, a drop in the average cost from 17 to 7 was observed when removing the second most important species from the sparse optimized PV definition, *i.e.*, when removing the pre-

ignition species HO_2 from the definition. Table S2 gives the QoI costs for the parameterizations with the sparse optimized PV definitions with two and one species left, *i.e.*, $\{\text{H}_2\text{O}, \text{HO}_2\}$ and $\{\text{H}_2\text{O}\}$ respectively. We observe that the cost for the pre-ignition species HO_2 and H_2O_2 significantly increases as expected with the removal of HO_2 from the sparse definition. However, the cost of NO and NO_2 drops even more causing the average cost to drop from 17 to 7. Fig. S4 explains the drop in cost of the NO_x species by plotting one trajectory of Y_{NO} *vs.* each PV (at $f = 0.4336$). With two species remaining in the sparse optimized PV definition, the PV is non-monotonic in the region where NO and NO_2 have their highest gradients causing a very large cost of 121 and 145. Once HO_2 is removed from the definition, only H_2O remains in the sparse definition and this naturally restores the monotonicity of the PV with as consequence the drop of the cost for NO and NO_2 . Note that the cost for these two species remains high due to their high gradients near $Y_{\text{PV}} = 1$ when the PV is only defined by H_2O .

	H_2O_2	H_2O	H_2	HO_2	N_2O	NO_2	NO	O_2	OH	T	$\dot{\omega}_{\text{PV}}$
$\text{PV}_{\text{opt}} - 2$ species left	3.4	1.0	0.9	0.9	1.5	120.5	145.2	1.0	1.3	1.2	1.3
$\text{PV}_{\text{opt}} - 1$ species left	25.9	0.8	0.8	9.4	1.0	26.4	61.2	0.8	0.9	0.9	1.0

Table S2: QoI costs for the manifolds parametrized by the sparse optimized PVs defined by the two most important species $\{\text{H}_2\text{O}, \text{HO}_2\}$ and the most important species $\{\text{H}_2\text{O}\}$.

Fig. S4: Evolution of Y_{NO} over the sparse optimized PV defined by the two most important species $\{\text{H}_2\text{O}, \text{HO}_2\}$ and the most important species $\{\text{H}_2\text{O}\}$. (a) Evolution of Y_{NO} over the complete range of the PVs. (b) Evolution of Y_{NO} on the last section of the PV where the non-uniqueness is revealed for the sparse optimized PV with two most important species left in the definition.

S2 A priori analysis: Heuristic *vs.* optimized PV

This section provides extra information about the *a priori* analysis performed in Section 5 of the main paper.

S2.1 Autoignition dataset

S2.1.1 Heuristic PVs: determination of the weights

In Section 3.1 of the main paper, two heuristic PVs were introduced which required the determination of a weight “w”, *i.e.*, $\text{H}_2\text{O} + w \text{HO}_2$ and $\text{H}_2\text{O} + w \text{NO}$. We decided to determine the weight from the set $\{1, 2, 10, 100, 1000\}$ for which the average cost was the lowest. As an additional indicator, we computed also the average validation MSE on all QoIs using an artificial neural network (ANN) as described in Section 2.4.1.

From Tables S3 and S4, we observe that the MSE is highly correlated to the cost meaning that the weight corresponding to the lowest cost effectively provides a good parameterization for which an accurate ANN can be built. For $\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{w HO}_2$, a weight of 10 provides the smallest average cost and MSE. For $\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{w NO}$, a weight of 1 provides the smallest cost and the MSE is close to the lowest MSE obtained with a weight of 2, *i.e.*, 3.3×10^{-4} and 3.1×10^{-4} respectively.

$\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{w HO}_2$	Cost	MSE (10^{-4})
1	6.48	8.6
2	6.35	8.5
10	6.17	7.4
100	7.51	9.1
1000	46.32	827.0

Table S3: Average cost and validation MSE for the heuristic parameterization employing $\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{w HO}_2$ where the weight “w” is varied with values 1, 2, 10, 100 and 1000.

$\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{w NO}$	Cost	MSE (10^{-4})
1	2.319	3.3
2	2.325	3.1
10	2.71	3.7
100	2.88	8.0
1000	25.50	175.4

Table S4: Average cost and validation MSE for the heuristic parameterization employing $\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{w NO}$ where the weight “w” is varied with values 1, 2, 10, 100 and 1000.

S2.1.2 f -PV manifolds

To visually observe how the optimized PV changes the manifold parameterization of the different QoIs compared to heuristic PVs for the autoignition dataset as a complement of what was shown in Section 5.1 of the main paper, Figs. S5-S8 show the f -PV manifolds colored by the different QoIs for the different heuristic and optimized PVs respectively. The figures illustrate clearly how the bottom and top regions of the manifold have been stretched out with the optimized PV compared to heuristic PVs. Additionally, the weights of every input species defining the optimized PV are provided in Table S5.

Fig. S5: Heuristic f -PV parameterization ($Y_{\text{PV}} = \text{H}_2\text{O} - \text{O}_2 - \text{H}_2$) colored by every QoI.

Fig. S6: Heuristic f -PV parameterization ($Y_{PV} = \text{H}_2\text{O} + 10 \text{HO}_2$) colored by every QoI.

Fig S7 shows for the parameterization with $Y_{PV} = \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{NO}$ that the manifolds colored by NO_2 and NO are stretched out in the upper region of the manifold compared to the parameterization with $Y_{PV} = \text{H}_2\text{O} - \text{O}_2 - \text{H}_2$ owing to the addition of NO in the PV definition. Similarly in Fig. S6 for $Y_{PV} = \text{H}_2\text{O} + 10 \text{HO}_2$, the bottom region of the manifold is slightly stretched out owing to the presence of HO_2 in the PV definition, which is noticeable for the manifolds colored by H_2O_2 and HO_2 .

Fig. S7: Heuristic f -PV parameterization ($Y_{PV} = \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{NO}$) colored by every QoI.

H ₂ NN	H ₂ O ₂	H ₂ O	H ₂	HNO	HO ₂	HONO ₂	HONO	H	
-7.7e-05	-8.1e-02	2.1e-03	-2.4e-148	4.6e-03	1.0	-4.9e-06	1.0e-05	-1.5e-02	
N ₂ O	NH ₂	NH	NNH	NO ₂	NO	N	O ₂	OH	O
1.1e-01	1.2e-03	1.6e-02	1.8e-03	-2.9e-03	9.1e-03	1.0e-03	3.9e-07	4.8e-29	-6.7e-04

Table S5: Weight of every species for the optimized PV definition of the autoignition dataset.

Fig. S8: The optimized f -PV parameterization colored by every QoI.

S2.1.3 Comparison with manifold parameterizations obtained with PCA

Similarly as shown in previous works [2, 3, 4, 5], we show in Fig. S9 that the manifold parameterizations obtained with PCA are suboptimal compared to the optimized parameterization obtained with the encoder-decoder. The figure shows the manifold parameterization obtained employing PCA for the autoignition dataset applying different input scalings. All species were included at the input, except N₂, N₂H₃ and H₂NN, which were constant or too small and therefore excluded to avoid numerical instabilities when performing the eigenvalue decomposition. Visually, the manifolds exhibit distorted shapes and overlapping regions which are the first indication of poor manifold parameterization. This is confirmed by the average cost function over the set of QoIs $\{T, Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2}, Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}, Y_{\text{H}_2}, Y_{\text{HO}_2}, Y_{\text{N}_2\text{O}}, Y_{\text{NO}_2}, Y_{\text{NO}}, Y_{\text{O}_2}, Y_{\text{OH}}\}$, excluding the two PC source terms to make the metric comparable with the average cost function of manifolds parametrized by mixture fraction and progress variable (PV), where the PV source term is also excluded from the set of QoIs. The best PCA parameterizations, with scalings “auto”, “range” and “max”, perform better than the heuristic parameterizations, with H₂O - O₂ - H₂, H₂O + 10 HO₂ and H₂O + NO having an average cost respectively of 2.61, 6.79 and 2.55, compared to 0.7-0.85 for the best PCA parameterizations. However, the optimized parameterization performs better than the PCA parameterizations, with an average cost of 0.37. This illustrates one major drawback of PCA. PCA does not allow to learn dimensions that best complement any user-selected physical dimensions like the mixture fraction, the dissipation rate, the enthalpy defect, etc. On the other hand, the encoder-decoder architecture addresses this problem neatly.

Fig. S9: The PCA parameterizations, preprocessed with different scalings, provide poorer manifold parameterizations compared to the optimized one ($\mathcal{L} = 0.37$) for the autoignition dataset. Each PCA parameterization is colored by three species, indicators of the main region manifolds: HO_2 (first row), NO (second row) and H_2O (third row).

S2.2 Flamelet dataset

S2.2.1 Heuristic PVs: determination of the weights

We performed the same analysis on the determination of the weights for the heuristic PVs $\text{H}_2\text{O} + w \text{HO}_2$ and $\text{H}_2\text{O} + w \text{NO}$ for the flamelet dataset as for the autoignition dataset described in Section S2.1.1. The same observation is done here, *i.e.*, a high correlation between the average cost and the MSE. For both $\text{H}_2\text{O} + w \text{HO}_2$ and $\text{H}_2\text{O} + w \text{NO}$, a weight “w” of 1000 provides the lowest cost. For $\text{H}_2\text{O} + 1000 \text{NO}$, it also gives the lowest MSE and for $\text{H}_2\text{O} + 1000 \text{HO}_2$, the MSE is close to the lowest MSE observed for $\text{H}_2\text{O} + 10 \text{HO}_2$ as shown in Tables S6 and S7.

$\text{H}_2\text{O} + w \text{HO}_2$	Cost	MSE (10^{-4})
1	4.8	16.1
2	4.6	16.8
10	4.4	16.3
100	4.9	39.7
1000	4.1	17.5

Table S6: Average cost and validation MSE for the heuristic parameterization employing $\text{H}_2\text{O} + w \text{HO}_2$ where the weight “w” is varied with values 1, 2, 10, 100 and 1000.

$\text{H}_2\text{O} + w \text{NO}$	Cost	MSE (10^{-4})
1	3.5	15.8
2	3.2	16.3
10	2.7	13.5
100	2.4	13.4
1000	2.1	11.1

Table S7: Average cost and validation MSE for the heuristic parameterization employing $\text{H}_2\text{O} + w \text{NO}$ where the weight “w” is varied with values 1, 2, 10, 100 and 1000.

S2.2.2 MSE vs. cost and f -PV manifolds figures including all heuristic PVs

For clarity, Fig. 10 in the main paper compared only the heuristic PV defined by $\text{H}_2\text{O} - \text{O}_2 - \text{H}_2$ with the optimized PV for the flamelet dataset. Here, Fig. S10 compares all heuristic PVs with the optimized PV employing the MSE and cost function metrics. The heuristic PV definition defined by $\text{H}_2\text{O} + 1000 \text{HO}_2$ performs the worst for most QoIs. This is explained by the large overlapping present in the manifold parameterization visible in Fig. S12. The heuristic PV defined as $\text{H}_2\text{O} + 1000 \text{NO}$ performs the best among the heuristic parameterizations and has the most similar manifold shape compared to the optimized PV, shown in Figs. S13 and S14 respectively. Both parameterizations expand the upper region of the manifold where many QoIs are present, explaining the improvements in MSE and cost. Nevertheless, the combination of multiple species discussed in Section S2.2.3 improves even further the optimized manifold parameterization compared to $\text{H}_2\text{O} + 1000 \text{NO}$. Additionally, the weights of every input species defining the optimized PV are provided in Table S8.

Fig. S10: (a) Cost and MSE for every QoI comparing *a priori* the different heuristic and optimized manifold parameterizations. The QoI are displayed from top to bottom in decreasing order of $\Delta_{MSE} = \log(|MSE_{Heu.} - MSE_{Opt.}|)$, corresponding to the length of the black line. (b) f -PV manifolds using the heuristic PV, defined as $Y_{H_2O} - Y_{H_2} - Y_{O_2}$, and the optimized PV colored by N₂O, OH, and H₂O.

Fig. S11: Heuristic f -PV parameterization ($Y_{PV} = H_2O - O_2 - H_2$) colored by every QoI for the flamelet dataset.

Fig. S12: Heuristic f -PV parameterization ($Y_{PV} = \text{H}_2\text{O} + 1000 \text{HO}_2$) colored by every QoI for the flamelet dataset.

Fig. S13: Heuristic f -PV parameterization ($Y_{PV} = \text{H}_2\text{O} + 1000 \text{NO}$) colored by every QoI for the flamelet dataset.

H_2NN	H_2O_2	H_2O	H_2	HNO	HO_2	HONO_2	HONO	H	
1.6e-07	5.6e-02	2.4e-04	-3.8e-04	3.1e-07	-5.0e-03	1.6e-05	-4.1e-05	-4.7e-03	
N_2O	NH_2	NH	NNH	NO_2	NO	N	O_2	OH	O
-1.0e+00	6.6e-06	2.6e-06	5.5e-05	1.3e-01	1.6e-01	-8.2e-06	-1.2e-15	-1.2e-03	-1.2e-03

Table S8: Weight of every species for the optimized PV definition of the flamelet dataset.

Fig. S14: The optimized f -PV parameterization colored by every QoI for the flamelet dataset.

S2.2.3 Effects of the encoder-decoder modifications and observations on the manifold topology

We used a flamelet dataset to illustrate that the modifications we applied on the encoder-decoder and the observations we made on the optimized PV, still held for another more complex case. Fig. S15 confirms the results discussed for the autoignition dataset in Section 4.

Multiple encoders-decoders were trained by varying the set of QoIs at the decoders' output and random seed, described in Table S9. Figure S15A confirms that the trainable scaling layer added prior to the encoder helps finding improved manifold parameterizations with on average a lower cost and MSE.

Fig. S15B compares parameterizations obtained from encoders-decoders with only the QoIs at the decoder in the linear scale *vs.* both QoIs in the linear and log scale. Including QoIs in the logarithmic scale improves the manifold parameterization indicated by the lower average cost for most points. For the parameterizations obtained with only the linear QoIs, one observation was excluded from the figure due to a poor final manifold parameterization.

Fig. S15C shows that the optimized PV obtained for the flamelet dataset can be sparsified to 9 species without affecting the manifold topology. Like for the autoignition dataset, the most important species is H_2O . Similarly, the third and fifth most important species of the optimized PVs, *i.e.*, NO and H_2O_2 , correspond between the two datasets. The presence of these species is explained by the fact that H_2O is required to track the overall progress of the hydrogen combustion, NO to track the NO_x formation and H_2O_2 to track the minor hydrogen species. The other two species present in the sparsified optimized PV definition for the autoignition case, *i.e.*, HO_2 and OH , are also present in the optimized PV definition of the flamelet dataset. One reason is the fact that in both cases the same species are targeted at the decoder's output.

Hyperset	$Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2}$	$Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	Y_{H_2}	Y_{HO_2}	$Y_{\text{N}_2\text{O}}$	Y_{NO_2}	Y_{NO}	Y_{O_2}	Y_{OH}
1	linear	linear	linear	linear	linear	linear	linear	linear	linear
2	log	log	log	log	log	log	log	log	log
3	lin + log	linear	linear	lin + log	linear	linear	linear	linear	linear
4	linear	linear	linear	linear	linear	lin + log	lin + log	linear	linear
5	lin + log	lin + log	lin + log	lin + log	lin + log	lin + log	lin + log	lin + log	lin + log

Table S9: Hyperparameters being varied to compare f -PV manifolds obtained with *vs.* without the trainable scaling layer for the flamelet dataset. The hyperparameters are the same as described in Section 3.2 except for the QoI set. Next to temperature and the PV source term, the species in the QoI set are in the original linear scale or transformed in the logarithmic scale.

(A) Similarly to the autoignition dataset, adding the scaling layer prior to the encoder for the flamelet dataset facilitates finding improved manifold parameterizations. (a) Average QoI cost, \mathcal{L}_{avg} , *vs.* the average MSE of all QoIs with and without the trainable scaling layer. (b) The PV source term cost, $\mathcal{L}_{\dot{\omega}_{\text{PV}}}$, *vs.* the average cost, \mathcal{L}_{avg} , with and without the trainable scaling layer.

(B) Optimized parameterizations obtained with encoders-decoders containing both QoIs in the linear and logarithmic scale at the decoder's output are better with respect to the cost function compared to those obtained with encoders-decoders containing only QoIs in the linear scale. The different observations correspond to different random seeds.

(C) The optimized PV definition can be reduced to 9 species without altering the manifold topology. The figure shows the evolution of the MSE and cost for all QoIs (top row) and for the PV source term alone (bottom row) when sparsifying the optimized PV by re-computing the metrics after removing the least important species at each step.

Fig. S15: Overview of the insights obtained for the flamelet dataset confirming the results obtained for the autoignition dataset discussed in Section 4 of the main paper.

S3 *A posteriori* analysis

This section provides extra information concerning the *a posteriori* analysis performed in Section 6 of the main paper. In the main paper, the results were only given for the fifth test trajectory, corresponding to trajectory number 4. In the following sections, the results for all test trajectories are provided. Additionally, further evidence is given concerning the sparse optimized PV *vs.* the original optimized PV for the *a posteriori* analysis.

S3.1 Transformation to a rectangular manifold

To increase the accuracy of the PV source term model, the manifolds were transformed to a rectangular shape [6]. This aligned the start and end of every trajectory helping the neural network to regress more accurately the PV source term in these regions. As an illustration, Fig. S16 compares the original *vs.* the rectangular manifold shape for both the heuristic ($Y_{PV} = \text{H}_2\text{O} - \text{O}_2 - \text{H}_2$) and optimized parameterization.

Fig. S16: The f -PV manifolds with the heuristic parametrized by $Y_{PV} = \text{H}_2\text{O} - \text{O}_2 - \text{H}_2$ (bottom) and optimized PV (top) comparing the original manifold shape (left) with the rectangular manifold (right).

S3.2 PV source term model: *A priori* performance

Once the PV source term model was trained, we measured how the model could predict pointwisely every PV source term from the test trajectory. This is a way to measure how well the model performs *a priori*. Figs. S17-S21 show the *a priori* performance for the different heuristic and optimized PVs respectively. To have a complete analysis, the heuristic PV defined as $Y_{PV} = \text{H}_2\text{O}$ has been added as fourth heuristic PV.

Fig. S22 compares two PV source term models, parametrized by the $Y_{PV} = \text{H}_2\text{O} - \text{O}_2 - \text{H}_2$ and the optimized PV respectively, employing the relative error, defined in Section 2.4.2 of the main paper. We notice a systematic difference between the PV source term models based on the heuristic *vs.* optimized parameterizations at the beginning of the trajectory from $t = 0\text{s}$ to $t = 0.05\text{s}$, corresponding to the region near IC. The PV source term models parametrized by the different heuristic PVs systematically underpredict the PV source term due to the small PV source term values being highly compressed in that region.

Fig. S17: *A priori* predictions of the PV source term for all ten test trajectories using the PV source term ANN model trained on the heuristic PV ($Y_{PV} = \text{H}_2\text{O} - \text{O}_2 - \text{H}_2$).

Fig. S18: *A priori* predictions of the PV source term for all ten test trajectories using the PV source term ANN model trained on the heuristic PV ($Y_{PV} = \text{H}_2\text{O} + 10 \text{HO}_2$).

Fig. S19: *A priori* predictions of the PV source term for all ten test trajectories using the PV source term ANN model trained on the heuristic PV ($Y_{PV} = \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{NO}$).

Fig. S20: *A priori* predictions of the PV source term for all ten test trajectories using the PV source term ANN model trained on the heuristic PV ($Y_{PV} = \text{H}_2\text{O}$).

Fig. S21: *A priori* predictions of the PV source term for all ten test trajectories using the PV source term ANN model trained on the optimized PV.

Fig. S22: The instantaneous relative error, defined as $\epsilon_{rel}(\dot{\omega}_{PV}(t)) = \frac{|\dot{\omega}_{PV, pred}(t) - \dot{\omega}_{PV, true}(t)|}{|\dot{\omega}_{PV, true}(t)|}$, with $\dot{\omega}_{PV, pred}(t)$ being the source term predicted by the PV source term model and $\dot{\omega}_{PV, true}(t)$ the true PV source term, for the prediction of the source term along the ten test trajectories using two PV source term models parametrized by the heuristic PV $Y_{PV} = H_2O - O_2 - H_2$ and the optimized PV respectively.

S3.3 Evolving the PV over time

Figs. S23-S27 show the evolved PV trajectory, obtained with the PV source term model parametrized by the different heuristic and optimized PVs respectively, *vs.* the true trajectory, obtained with the full-order model, for all ten test trajectories. We observe a constant ignition delay of around 0.5s for the ROM parametrized by the heuristic PV ($Y_{PV} = \text{H}_2\text{O} - \text{O}_2 - \text{H}_2$) while on the contrary the ignition delay stays around 0.005s for the ROM parametrized by the optimized PV. For the heuristic PVs ($Y_{PV} = \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{NO}$ and $Y_{PV} = \text{H}_2\text{O}$), no ignition is observed due to the underprediction of the PV source term at the start of the simulation as observed in Figs. S19-S20. Concerning the heuristic PV ($Y_{PV} = \text{H}_2\text{O} + 10 \text{HO}_2$), the ignition delay stays around 0.025s owing to a more accurate PV source term model which is itself explained by the fact that the small values of the PV source term are better parametrized, *i.e.*, smaller range of PV source term values.

Fig. S23: Comparison of the true PV trajectory obtained with the full-order model (FOM) with the one obtained by the reduced-order model (ROM), evolving the PV over time employing the PV source term ANN model parametrized by the heuristic PV ($Y_{PV} = \text{H}_2\text{O} - \text{O}_2 - \text{H}_2$), for all ten test trajectories.

Fig. S24: Comparison of the true PV trajectory obtained with the full-order model (FOM) with the one obtained by the reduced-order model (ROM), evolving the PV over time employing the PV source term ANN model parametrized by the heuristic PV ($Y_{PV} = \text{H}_2\text{O} + 10 \text{HO}_2$), for all ten test trajectories.

Fig. S25: Comparison of the true PV trajectory obtained with the full-order model (FOM) with the one obtained by the reduced-order model (ROM), evolving the PV over time employing the PV source term ANN model parametrized by the heuristic PV ($Y_{PV} = \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{NO}$), for all ten test trajectories.

Fig. S26: Comparison of the true PV trajectory obtained with the full-order model (FOM) with the one obtained by the reduced-order model (ROM), evolving the PV over time employing the PV source term ANN model parametrized by the heuristic PV ($Y_{PV} = \text{H}_2\text{O}$), for all ten test trajectories.

Fig. S27: Comparison of the true PV trajectory obtained with the full-order model (FOM) with the one obtained by the reduced-order model (ROM), evolving the PV over time employing the PV source term ANN model parametrized by the optimized PV, for all ten test trajectories.

S3.4 Origin of the QoI regression improvements

We observed in Section 5.1 of the main paper with Fig. 7 that the ANN parametrized by the optimized PV had a lower MSE for regressing every QoI compared to the one parametrized by the heuristic PVs. As a consequence, the full state-space model parametrized by the optimized PV was more accurate in reconstructing the different QoIs during the ROM simulations. To better understand where the improvements were originating from, we measured pointwisely the difference in MSE for every point of the manifold and for every QoI individually. Fig. S28 shows the points from the validation dataset where the ANN parametrized by the heuristic PV ($Y_{PV} = \text{H}_2\text{O} - \text{O}_2 - \text{H}_2$) has a lower MSE than the ANN parametrized by the optimized PV and the difference is computed as $\log(\text{MSE}_{\text{opt}} - \text{MSE}_{\text{heu}})$, indicating in the logarithmic scale with how many orders of magnitude these points are more accurately regressed with the heuristic PV. The opposite rationale holds for Fig. S29 where it shows all the points where the ANN parametrized by the optimized PV regresses more accurately and the error is computed as $\log(\text{MSE}_{\text{heu}} - \text{MSE}_{\text{opt}})$. We observe from the two figures that more points are present in Fig. S29 meaning that the ANN parametrized by the optimized PV regresses more points accurately. Moreover, looking at the colorbar range, we observe in Fig. S28 the improvements with the ANN parametrized by the heuristic PV are maximally around 10^{-8} to 10^{-10} , while in Fig. S29 the difference in MSE can be of the order 10^0 when the ANN parametrized by the optimized PV is more accurate. Looking more in detail to the different colorbars of Fig. S29, the largest improvements are for the minor species and NO_x species, corresponding to the species which are the most affected by the manifold topology modification induced by the optimized PV, which was already observed in Fig. 7 of the main paper. From the Fig. S29, we learn that the largest improvements in MSE are located where the manifold has been stretched out by the optimized PV, *i.e.*, the lower and upper regions of the manifold corresponding to the regions near IC and SS. The species benefit the most from the stretched out manifold where the highest gradients are present for that species. For H_2O_2 and HO_2 , it corresponds to the bottom region of the manifold. For the NO_x species, it corresponds to the upper region of the manifold.

Fig. S28: Points from the validation dataset which are more accurately regressed by the ANN parametrized with the heuristic PV ($Y_{PV} = \text{H}_2\text{O} - \text{O}_2 - \text{H}_2$) *vs.* the optimized PV. The difference in error is measured by $\log(\text{MSE}_{\text{opt}} - \text{MSE}_{\text{heu}})$.

Fig. S29: Points from the validation dataset which are more accurately regressed by the ANN parametrized with the optimized PV *vs.* the heuristic PV ($Y_{PV} = \text{H}_2\text{O} - \text{O}_2 - \text{H}_2$). The difference in error is measured by $\log(\text{MSE}_{\text{heu}} - \text{MSE}_{\text{opt}})$.

S3.5 Error accumulation analysis

To better understand the error accumulation when evolving the PV over time, Fig. S30 illustrates for the fifth test trajectory the *a priori* and *a posteriori* evolution of the PV source term prediction by the PV source term models parametrized by the heuristic PV ($Y_{PV} = \text{H}_2\text{O} - \text{O}_2 - \text{H}_2$) and the optimized PV. Additionally, the figure quantifies over time the absolute and relative PV error, *i.e.*, $PV_{\text{true}} - PV_{\text{pred}}$ and $(PV_{\text{true}} - PV_{\text{pred}})/PV_{\text{true}}$ respectively, with PV_{true} and PV_{pred} being the true and predicted PV value at timestep t .

As seen previously in Section S3.2, the heuristic PV source term model underpredicts *a priori* the PV source term value for $t = 0s - 0.04s$, which is shown again in the first subplot of Fig. S30. On the contrary, the second subplot of Fig. S30 indicates that the PV source term model parametrized by the optimized PV predicts *a priori* accurately the PV source term values over the complete simulation time. The third subplot shows that the PV error increases over time for both parameterizations with a steep increase at ignition. Overall, the optimized PV has a higher absolute error from initial conditions to ignition compared to the heuristic PV. The error drops for the optimized PV once the ROM predicts the ignition. In relative PV values, shown in the fourth subplot, the relative is higher for the optimized PV only at the beginning. As the fifth subplot illustrates, the PV source term model for the heuristic PV underpredicts the PV source

values over the complete simulation time, which leads to a continuously increasing relative PV error since the heuristic PV lag increases over the simulation. On the other hand, the optimized PV builds up a small time lag at the beginning, suggested by the small *a priori* and *a posteriori* underprediction at the beginning. Thereafter, the relative PV error for the optimized PV stays constant till ignition as the PV source term model parametrized by the optimized PV predicts perfectly the PV source term. Hence, the ignition prediction for the optimized PV is shifted only due to the error at the beginning of the trajectory.

Fig. S30: Visualization of the error accumulation for the fifth test trajectory comparing the PV source term models parametrized by heuristic PV ($Y_{PV} = \text{H}_2\text{O} - \text{O}_2 - \text{H}_2$) and the optimized PV. First two rows present the *a priori* prediction of the PV source term, corresponding to the fifth test trajectory in Figs. S17 and S21. The third and fourth rows illustrate the absolute and relative error accumulation of the PVs over time. The last two rows present the *a posteriori* prediction of the PV source term.

S3.6 Reconstructing the QoIs given f and the evolved PV

Figs. S31-S32 show the reconstructed QoIs by the ROMs parametrized by the different heuristic and optimized PVs respectively for all ten test trajectories except the fifth trajectory shown in the main paper. Similar trends as for the fifth test trajectory can be observed, *i.e.*, ignition delay, misprediction of the peak value at ignition and misprediction of the QoI value at steady-state, for the ROM parametrized by the heuristic PVs compared to one parametrized by the optimized PV.

Fig. S31: Comparison of the full-order model (FOM) with the ROMs parametrized by the different heuristic and optimized PVs for the prediction of the species and temperature of the first four test trajectories.

Fig. S32: Comparison of the full-order model (FOM) with the ROMs parametrized by the different heuristic and optimized PVs for the prediction of the species and temperature of the last five test trajectories.

S3.7 *A posteriori* analysis: sparse vs. original optimized PV

We showed in the main paper that the optimized PV could be sparsified without altering the manifold topology and we briefly mentioned in Section 6 that the *a posteriori* simulations with the original and sparse optimized PVs gave very similar results. With Fig. S33, we complete the comparison between the sparse and original optimized PV by providing the error distribution over all ten test trajectories when performing *a posteriori* simulations with ROMs parametrized respectively with the sparse and original optimized PV. From the figure, we observe no significant difference between the two ROMs having every error distribution in the same range, further confirming that there is no significant difference between the two PVs. The small variations in distribution between the two parameterizations are mainly explained by the variability present during the training of the ANNs for the PV source term model and the full state-space model.

Fig. S33: Distribution of the relative error on max value $\varepsilon_{i,j}^{\max}$ and relative error on the steady-state value $\varepsilon_{i,j}^{\text{SS}}$, introduced in Section 2.4.2 of the main paper, over all ten test trajectories for both ROMs parametrized by the sparse and original optimized PV.

S3.8 *A posteriori* analysis: Bilinear interpolation via tabulation

To illustrate that the insights obtained in the main paper hold independently of the regression method used during the ROM simulations, the *a posteriori* simulations performed in Section 6 of the main paper are repeated with bilinear interpolation via tabulation instead of ANNs. This means that both the PV source term model and the full state-space model are using tabulation using the training data to regress respectively the PV source term and the state-space.

Fig. S34 shows for the fifth test trajectory how the different ROMs using interpolation predict the PV trajectory. Compared to the heuristic PVs, the ROM using the optimized parameterization predicts more accurately the ignition time. This is confirmed in Table S10 where on average the optimized PV is two orders of magnitude more accurate on predicting the ignition time compared to the heuristic PVs.

Reconstructing subsequently the full state-space with also tabulation, we show in Fig. S35 the distribution of the relative error on the max value and the steady-state error similarly as in Fig. 15 of the main paper. For both metrics, the optimized parameterization has systematically the lowest error. On the prediction of the max value, differences are mostly noticeable between the heuristic and the optimized PVs for the species where large gradients are present, *i.e.*, H_2O_2 , NO_2 , NO_2 and temperature. For the prediction on the steady-state error, the differences are less pronounced since it is based on the prediction of the last point of the trajectory. With tabulation, this prediction is performed perfectly as it will be independent of the manifold shape.

Using bilinear interpolation with tabulation inside the ROM, a regression method without training error, provides the same conclusions as with the ANN. The key manifold regions being stretched out using the optimized parameterization lead to a more accurate ROM. Hence, this provides further evidence that the

differences in accuracy observed with the ANN are not related to the training of the ANN, but that it is intrinsically related to the input parameterization.

Note that tabulation is more accurate than the ANN, but has the major drawback of requiring a lot of memory to store the data, especially when the dataset becomes very large, and tabulation is slow at inference.

Fig. S34: Evolved PV trajectories for the fifth test trajectory employing ROMs parametrized by the different PVs with tabulation. The top row shows the full trajectory and the bottom row zooms in on the ignition region.

PV	Mean \pm Std (%)
$\text{H}_2\text{O} - \text{O}_2 - \text{H}_2$	0.49 ± 0.21
H_2O	6.18 ± 1.50
$\text{H}_2\text{O} + 10 \text{HO}_2$	0.32 ± 0.017
$\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{NO}$	6.21 ± 1.51
Optimized	0.0087 ± 0.0064

Table S10: Mean and standard deviation of the ignition time delay expressed in percentage, averaged over the ten test trajectories, for every parameterization using tabulation.

Fig. S35: Distribution of the relative error on max value $\varepsilon_{i,j}^{\max}$ and relative error on the steady-state value $\varepsilon_{i,j}^{\text{SS}}$, introduced in Section 2.4.2, over all ten test trajectories for both ROMs parametrized by the heuristic and optimized PV.

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